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Research Article

FREQUENCY OF HYDROCEPHALUS IN CASES OF TBM

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Abstract:**Objectives:** To determine the frequency of hydrocephalus in cases of TBM.**Material & methods;** This was a cross sectional study conducted at different centers of Sargodha and Lahore from January 2019 to September 2019. The detailed demographic data was collected. The cases of TBM were selected on clinical and laboratory diagnosis and then they underwent CT scan of brain (plain) and diagnosis of TBM was made in BMRC scale. **Results;** In the present study there were total 100 cases of TBM, out of which 60 (60%) were males and 40 (40%) females with mean age of 47.23 ± 10.39 years. There were 6 (6%) cases in stage I, 65 (65%) in II and 29 (29%) in stage III of TBM. Hydrocephalus was observed in 48 (48%) of the cases. There was no significant difference in terms of gender and age groups with *p* values of 0.67 and 0.58 respectively. The results were significantly higher in those that had stage III of TBM where it was seen in 19 (65.52%) out of 29 cases as compared to 27 (41.54%) cases in stage II and 2 (33.33%) in stage I of their respective groups with *p* value of 0.02. **Conclusion;** Hydrocephalus is seen nearly in half of the cases with TBM and it is significantly high in cases that had stage III of TBM.**Key words;** TBM, hydrocephalus.**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the commonest chronic infectious diseases and highest burden is seen in the developing countries especially Pakistan and is the disease of the ancient times. Its number was declining in the developed countries but the rate is re inclining due to emergence of Human immune deficiency virus (HIV). According to a survey about one third of the world is exposed to it and in Pakistan the incidence is 275/100000 population¹.

Tuberculosis is mainly the disease of the lungs but the spread to any of the viscera is possible and it has wide range of clinical presentation that can mimic the various diseases and hence lead to ultimate delay in the diagnosis which can further increase the morbidity and mortality in such cases.

Central nervous system (CNS) TB is also not uncommon and can present in various ways. Tuberculoma, Tuberculous meningitis (TBM), encephalitis are the different complications and TBM is the most common one, TBM can be a fatal complication. It leads to hindrance in the flow of cerebrospinal fluid and leading to hydrocephalus that can also lead to functional, behavioral, psychological impertinent.

Despite the recent advancements in the diagnostic modalities, the diagnosis of TBM is still a dilemma and largely relies upon characteristic CSF picture and on microbiological methods of detection of Acid-Fast Bacilli (AFB) smear on cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) or CSF culture for AFB. The yield is yet low for both of these due to low organism burden. Anti-tuberculosis therapy (ATT) is the treatment of choice.

TBM can present with complaints of fever, weight loss, photophobia, headache, vomiting, cranial nerve palsies and altered level of consciousness that can be classified on the basis of British Medical Research Council contemporary clinical criteria (BMRC) for TBM into three stages². Furthermore, TBM can complicate into seizure disorder, hydrocephalus, hearing loss, tuberculous rediculomyelitis (rare) with different degree of preordance. The rate of hydrocephalus in TBM varied from 20%³ to 65%⁴ in countries where TB prevalence is high.

OBJECTIVE:

To determine the frequency of hydrocephalus in cases of Tuberculous meningitis.

Study settings;

Multi centre study at Sargodha and Lahore

Study duration;

January 2019 to September 2019

Study design;

Cross sectional study

Sampling technique;

Non probability consecutive sampling

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Both genders
2. All adults with age more than 15 years
3. Cases of TBM as per operational definition.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Cases with previous history of head trauma
2. Cases with end stage liver or renal failure
3. Cases with known CNS malignancy

Tuberculous Meningitis (TBM);

It was labeled on the presence of fever, headache, with or without vomiting and seizure along with following data.

a) Positive AFB smear or culture on CSF

b) Typical CSF exudative lymphocytic picture of

- CSF Lymphocyte 20-500/mm³
- CSF protein more than 100 mg/dl
- CSF glucose < 60% of plasma glucose

BMRC contemporary clinical criteria for TBM;

It was divided into 3 stages.

- **Stage I:** Alert and oriented without focal neurological deficits and GCS is 15/15.
- **Stage II:** Glasgow coma score of 11-14 or 15 with focal neurological deficits.
- **Stage III:** Glasgow coma score of 10 or less, with or without focal neurological deficits.

Hydrocephalus;

It was labeled on assessment on CT brain (plain) by dilatation of ventricle size by 25% of its normal size.

Statistical analysis;

The detailed sociodemographic and clinical data was collected. Data was analyzed with the help of SPSS version 23. Effect modifiers will be controlled through stratification and post stratification Chi-Square test was applied taking P-value < 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

In the present study there were total 100 cases of TBM, out of which 60 (60%) were males and 40 (40%) females with mean age of 47.23±10.39 years. There were 6 (6%) cases in stage I, 65 (65%) in II and 29 (29%) in stage III of TBM. Hydrocephalus was observed in 48 (48%) of the cases. There was no significant difference in terms of gender and age groups with p values of 0.67 and 0.58 respectively in table 1 and table 2. The results were significantly higher in those that had stage III of TBM where it was seen in 19 (65.52%) out of 29 cases as compared to 27 (41.54%) cases in stage II and 2 (33.33%) in stage I of their respective groups with p value of 0.02 as in table 03.

DISCUSSION:

Tuberculosis is one of the most dreadful infectious disease of the ancient times as it can involve any organ and its vague presentation can pose a diagnostic delay and ultimately fatal outcome can be seen, especially in

cases of CNS involvement in the form of tuberculous meningitis which can be life threatening.

Hydrocephalus was observed in 48 (48%) of the cases in the present study. These results were similar to the studies done in the same vicinities of the under developed countries where it was observed in about 60% of the cases in a study conducted by Nabi S et al.⁹ However, the study conducted by Chan et al found relatively lower incidence rate and in their study it was seen in only 29% of the cases.¹⁰ The reason of this high number in present and the study by Nabi S et al an be explained that these both studies were conducted in the developing country as compared to the later one which has a slight better socioeconomic and health care facilities.

There was no significant different in terms of gender in both groups; however male gender had this in higher number where it was seen in 30 (50%) of the cases with p value of 0.67. These results were similar to the

study done by Kumar R and Christensen AS et al that also found males with higher no of hydrocephalus but non-significant difference.¹¹⁻¹²

The results were significantly higher in those that had stage III of TBM where it was seen in 19 (65.52%) out of 29 cases as compared to 27 (41.54%) cases in stage II and 2 (33.33%) in stage I of their respective groups with p value of 0.02. These results were also strengthened by the study of Chan et al who also found highest number of cases that had hydrocephalus in stage II and III where its was seen in almost 90% of the cases combined.¹⁰ Similar sorts of results were observed by Salekeen S and Newton RW et al, however they did not find any significant difference.¹³⁻¹⁴

CONCLUSION:

Hydrocephalus is seen nearly in half of the cases with TBM and it is significantly high in cases that had stage III of TBM.

TABLE 1: HYDROCEPHALUS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER IN TBM
n=100

Gender	Hydrocephalus		Total
	Yes	No	
Male	30 (50%)	30 (50%)	60 (100%)
Female	18 (45%)	22 (55%)	40 (100%)
Total	48 (48%)	52 (52%)	100 (100%)

p = 0.67

TABLE 2: HYDROCEPHALUS WITH RESPECT TO AGE GROUPS IN TBM
n=100

Age Group	Hydrocephalus		Total
	Yes	No	
15 to 40	29 (46.03%)	16 (53.97%)	63 (100%)
> 40	19 (51.35%)	03 (48.65%)	37 (100%)
Total	48 (48%)	52 (52%)	100 (100%)

p = 0.58

TABLE 3: HYDROCEPHALUS WITH RESPECT TO STAGE OF TBM
n=100

Stage of TBM	Hydrocephalus		Total
	Yes	No	
I	02 (33.33%)	04 (66.67%)	06 (100%)
II	27 (41.54%)	38 (58.46%)	65 (100%)
III	19 (65.52%)	10 (34.48%)	29 (100%)
Total	48 (48%)	52 (52%)	100 (100%)

p = 0.02

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